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Review Article:

The Visionary Behind Forensic Nursing: The Legacy of Virginia Anne Lynch

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Abstract: Forensic nursing is the nursing practice that combines healthcare with the judicial system. Virginia Anne Lynch is recognized as the pioneer of forensic nursing. She created the initial forensic nursing curriculum and founded the International Association of Forensic Nurses (IAFN), a professional body for registered nurses practicing forensic nursing engaged in the care of victims of trauma and violence. Lynch structured the standard of forensic nursing practices for the care and examination of victims of trauma and violence, especially sexual assault. She helped forensic nursing become a distinct specialty and expanded the scope of the specialty. Lynch also authored numerous texts on forensic nursing. The article explores the life of Virginia Anee Lynch, her significant contributions to forensic nursing, and her lasting impact on the nursing profession and the criminal justice system.

Keywords: Virginia Anne Lynch, Forensic Nursing, Sexual Assault Nurse Examiner, Forensic Nurse Examiner

Introduction and Background: Virginia Anne Lynch, a pioneer in forensic nursing as she

envisioned, unified the two disciplines, healthcare, and the criminal justice system, into one practice. This article delves into the career and founding work on forensic nursing by Lynch. Lynch defined forensic nursing as "the application of the forensic aspects of healthcare combined with the bio/psycho/social/spiritual education of the registered nurse in the scientific investigation and treatment of trauma or death of victims and perpetrators of violence, criminal activity, and traumatic accidents." Her efforts are considered significant in providing structured nursing practices for the care of trauma and violence victims [1].

Early Life and Education:

Virginia Anne Lynch was born on January 27, 1941, in Weatherford, Texas, United States. She obtained her Associate of Arts degree from Weatherford College, Texas, in 1979. Lynch grew up with a strong interest in both science and care for others, which led her to pursue a career in nursing after obtaining her Bachelor of Science in Nursing from Texas Christian University in 1982. Lynch began her career in

clinical settings where she frequently encountered cases involving victims of violence. She was an assistant head nurse surgery at All Saints Hospital, Fort Worth, from 1982 to 1983. Lynch then worked as a registered nurse in emergency surgery at Campbell Memorial Hospital, Weatherford, Texas, from 1983 to 1984. As a medicolegal death investigator at the Tarrant County Medical Examiner's District in Fort Worth from 1984 to 1990. These early experiences highlighted for her a critical gap in the healthcare system's ability to address the forensic needs of these victims, which often left vital evidence uncollected and victim care incomplete. She completed her Master of Science in Nursing (MSN) at the University of Texas, Arlington, in 1990, where she completed her dissertation on 'Clinical Forensic Nursing: A descriptive study in role development' [2,3].

Methodology: This review article primarily focuses on the contributions of Virginia Anne Lynch in developing the specialty of forensic nursing. A comprehensive literature search was conducted on Google Scholar to find articles and book

chapters discussing Lynch's work and the history of forensic nursing. The search was conducted using the keywords "Virginia Anne Lynch," "forensic nursing pioneer," and "history of forensic nursing." Articles and book chapters mentioning Virginia Anne Lynch's contributions to forensic nursing and the history and evolution of forensic nursing were included in this review article. All the relevant literature to date was included.

Review: The Birth of Forensic Nursing, Professionalization and Expansion

Victims of trauma and violence, such as sexual assault, were often retraumatized during the procedure of medical examination, as the existing standard of examination was deficient in providing trauma approach care, keeping in mind the specific needs of such victims. Also, untrained healthcare personnel often miss essential forensic evidence, compromising legal trial proceedings. Realizing these deficiencies, in 1991, the American Academy of Forensic Sciences (AAFS) requested Lynch to set up a role for forensic nurses in nursing practice. She developed the first formal

curriculum for forensic nursing, which was accepted by AAFS, followed by the recognition of forensic nursing as a distinct specialty in 1995 by the American Nurses Association (ANA) [4].

Lynch co-founded the International Association of Forensic Nurses (IAFN) in 1992, a professional body for registered nurses practicing forensic nursing. The term forensic nursing was accepted by nursing professionals assembled for a national convention at the University of Minnesota in 1992, and the gathering elected Lynch as the first president of IAFN and served as founding president till 1996 [5].

Lynch played a crucial role in the expansion of the sexual assault nurse examiner (SANE) and developed the standard of practice of SANEs and forensic nursing altogether. SANEs became fundamental to emergency departments and rape crisis centers indulged in trauma care of the victims of sexual crime. The nurses were trained to provide compassionate care, collect and preserve forensic evidence, conduct forensic interviews, and serve as expert witnesses in court [6]. After its origin in the United States,

forensic nursing expanded as a specialty in other countries such as Canada, South Africa, Singapore, Malaysia, Japan, India, etc. [7].

Introduction of Forensic Nursing in India

Virginia A. Lynch, during her first visit to India in December 2002, introduced the concept of forensic nursing in India along with Dr. R.K. Gorea, a forensic medicine specialist, to the nursing faculty and students at Sri Guru Har Sahai Nursing School, Raikot, Punjab. She extensively advocated the specialty to the doctors, nurses, and police officials during her visit to India. Lynch and Dr. Gorea formulated the first forensic nursing program at the Government Nursing School, Patiala, in 2002 [7,8]. Lynch continued her efforts and made subsequent visits to India to broaden the awareness of forensic nursing by giving talks at regional and national conferences on forensic medicine. This led to the acceptance of forensic nursing as a distinct specialty among forensic pathologists and police officials in India. Successively, in 2009, Gian Sagar Nursing College, Punjab, India, and Colorado University,

USA, where Lynch is faculty, collaborated to begin a forensic nursing program [7]. Recently, the Indian Nursing Council introduced forensic nursing in the undergraduate nursing curriculum and developed a program for a postgraduate diploma in forensic nursing [9].

Impact on Healthcare and Criminal Justice

Lynch's contribution to establishing a forensic nursing model that integrated the nursing practice with the criminal justice system and opened avenues for the nursing professional to play a vital role in response to trauma and crime, providing appropriate attention to the legal implications of such cases apart from the usual nursing care and intervention. The introduction of forensic nurses offered relief to the healthcare systems dealing with medicolegal cases. A forensic nurse examiner (FNE) in the emergency department ensures that essential forensic evidentiary materials are not lost because of the unavailability or delay in the arrival of forensic medical examiners [1].

Lynch developed forensic nursing protocols, which became standard practice in hospitals and health

facilities across the globe. Lynch and Dr RK Gorea outlined the tremendous scope of FNEs within the healthcare and criminal justice system. FNEs can play a part in the mortuary setup by being at the forefront of dealing with the queries of family members of the deceased and performing a pre-autopsy assessment of the case. In cases of victims of trauma and violence, assist in medicolegal documentation and preserve vital forensic evidence. SANE can develop a rapport with the victims of sexual assault, elucidate the appropriate history of the crime, aid in providing competent and empathetic care and examination, and even testify in a court of law. This is the reason why Western countries have started recognizing SANEs as expert witnesses under their judicial system, leading to an increase in the conviction rate. Forensic nurses can become part of the crime investigation team and assist the police and magistrates in collecting evidence using their knowledge of both medicine and law to an advantage. Forensic nurses can be instrumental in the mental health assessment of both the victim and the accused of a

crime. FNEs in poisoning cases can collect samples such as gastric lavage, urine, blood, etc. They can become an important member of the clinical setup by recognizing and reporting children with suspected abuse and neglect [7].

Educational Contributions and Career:

Virginia Anne Lynch is an educator, prolific author, and researcher apart from a forensic nurse. She drafted the first forensic nursing program and prepared the role of such specialist nurses in the healthcare and justice system in the United States, which was soon adopted and followed in other parts of the world. During the 1980s, Lynch established a clinic for the victims of sexual offenses in Parker County, Texas, and acted as a training specialist from 1982 to 1988. After completing her master's in nursing in 1990, she completed advanced death investigation studies at the Office of the Chief Medical Examiner (OCME) in New York City. She was a member of the rape crisis center victim-witness assistance program at Valdosta-Lowndes County, Georgia, from 1990 to 1992. In 1992, she obtained her coroner certification from the state of Georgia. She worked as

a nurse educator forensic science consultant at Barbara Clark Mims Associations, Lewisville, Texas, from 1991 to 1994. Presently, Lynch is a consultant in the Department of Nursing, University of Colorado Colorado Springs, United States, since 1995 [2,4,10].

She was Director at Forensic Nurse Consultants from 2000 to 2016. Virginia was the first Fulbright Scholar in India from 2005 to 2006 to study global health, focusing on forensic nursing science. Lynch also served as a visiting professor from 2016 to 2017 in international studies at the Japanese Red Cross Kyushu International College of Nursing in Munakata, Fukuoka, Japan [11].

Her book 'Forensic Nursing Science' released in 2006, followed by the publication of the second edition in 2010, is considered a cardinal literature of forensic nursing science, covering a wide range of topics, from the evolution of forensic nursing to detailed clinical protocols for evidence collections and forensic examinations, becoming a foundational resource for forensic nursing educations and practice [12]. She is the author

of multiple texts on forensic nursing, which creates awareness among the global masses about the specialty.

Legacy and Continuing Influence

The attempts made by Lynch formed one entire subspecialty in nursing and motivated so many nurses to take forensic nursing as their career worldwide. Due to her efforts, victims of trauma and violence received compassionate care alongside legal justice, solidifying her place as a leader in forensic nursing. Various subspecialties emerged within forensic nursing, such as clinical forensic nursing, SANE, forensic psychiatry nursing, pediatric forensic nursing, and correctional nursing. [9].

Lynch was named a fellow of the American Academy of Nursing (AAN) and was recognized as an outstanding alumna of Texas Christian University's Harris College of Nursing. Her dissertation, which helped to establish forensic nursing as a distinct scientific field, earned her a spot at the University of Texas at Arlington College of Nursing's Wall of Honour in 2008. She started a global outreach program in forensic nursing science in 2000, which includes social

advocacy, teaching, and consulting, and she is continuing to expand the services to other countries where the scope of forensic nursing is still unfamiliar. She received the 2014 'AAFS Kenneth S. Field Award of Appreciation for Outstanding Service' and the 2016 'John R. Hunt Award' for consistent contributions to forensic science. Lynch was showcased in the 2016 film "The American Nurse: A History of Challenge and Compassion," along with Florence Nightingale, Clara Barton, Linda Richards, and Mary Eliza Mahoney. Her most recent honor came from the AAFS Board of Directors, who, for her exceptional contributions to the field of forensic science, gave her the Distinguished Fellow Award for 2018. To continue Virginia's legacy and encourage professionals in nursing, IAFN's highest honor, the Virginia Lynch Pioneer Award in Forensic Nursing, is given annually since 1995 to someone who has made outstanding contributions to forensic nursing [10]. The timeline of key milestones in Lynch's career is highlighted in **Table 1:** Shows the timeline of key milestones in Virginia Anne Lynch's career.

Year	Key Highlights of Virginia Anne Lynch's Career and Contributions to Forensic Nursing		Nursing: A Descriptive Study in Role Development.'
1941	Born on January 27 in Weatherford, Texas, USA.	1991	Requested by the American Academy of Forensic Sciences (AAFS) to create a role for forensic nurses, leading to the development of the first formal forensic nursing curriculum.
1979	Obtained her Associate of Arts degree from Weatherford College, Texas.	1992	Co-founded the International Association of Forensic Nurses (IAFN) and was elected its first president, served until 1996.
1982	Graduated with a Bachelor of Science in Nursing from Texas Christian University. Began working as an Assistant Head Nurse at All Saints Hospital, Fort Worth.	1995	The American Nurses Association (ANA) officially recognized forensic nursing as a distinct specialty.
1983-1984	Worked as a Registered Nurse in Emergency Surgery at Campbell Memorial Hospital, Weatherford, Texas.	1995-Present	The Virginia Lynch Pioneer Award in Forensic Nursing, instituted in 1995, continues to be awarded annually to honor outstanding contributions to the field of forensic nursing
1984-1990	Served as a medicolegal death investigator at Tarrant County Medical Examiner's District, Fort Worth, Texas.	2000	Launched a global outreach program in forensic nursing science.
1990	Completed her Master of Science in Nursing (MSN) from the University of Texas, Arlington. Her dissertation focused on 'Clinical Forensic		

2002	Introduced forensic nursing in India and co-developed the first forensic nursing program with Dr R.K. Gorea in the country.
2005-2006	Became the first Fulbright Scholar in India, studying global health with a focus on forensic nursing science.
2006	Authored the book 'Forensic Nursing Science' followed by the second edition in 2010, with co-author Janet Barber Duval, published by Elsevier Mosby. This book became a foundational resource in forensic nursing education.
2008	Earned a spot at the University of Texas at Arlington College of Nursing's Wall of Honour.
2009	Collaborated with Gian Sagar Nursing College, Punjab, India, and Colorado University to start a forensic nursing program.
2014	Received 'American Academy of Forensic Sciences (AAFS) Kenneth S. Field Award

	of Appreciation for Outstanding Service.'
2016	Featured in the film 'The American Nurse: A History of Challenge and Compassion,' showcasing her contributions alongside historical nursing figures. Received 'John R. Hunt Award' for consistent contributions to forensic science from the American Academy of Forensic Sciences (AAFS).
2018	Received the Distinguished Fellow Award from the American Academy of Forensic Sciences (AAFS) for her exceptional contributions to forensic science.

Way forward for Forensic Nursing in India: The specialty of forensic nursing is very much developed in Western countries and thriving its presence in areas such as sexual assault victim examination, management of victims of trauma in emergency and clinical setting, forensic psychiatry, investigation of crime scenes, death investigation, etc.

However, it still has a long way to go in countries like India, where it has yet to be established as a distinct specialty and incorporated into the routine nursing practice. The foremost thing that is needed is to strengthen the nursing curriculum to integrate the wide variety of fields of forensic nursing. Development of more postgraduate or master's programs in forensic nursing is needed to have such nursing specialists working in various levels of healthcare facilities. The positions of SANE and FNE should be created in tertiary healthcare centers to provide care to provide healthcare and legal assistance under the same roof. A progressive step could be recognizing forensic nursing specialists as expert witnesses under Indian law, like in Western countries. This will further demonstrate their importance in the healthcare system and link them significantly with the criminal justice system.

Conclusion: The pioneering work of Virginia Anne Lynch linked the nursing profession, healthcare, and the law through forensic nursing. Her vision, dedication, and hard work helped to establish forensic nursing as

a specialty to give specialized care to victims of violence and trauma. Lynch's efforts have helped many patients receive better care and strengthened the criminal justice system's ability to prosecute offenders. Her efforts will continue helping future generations for years since her legacy inspires and directs the field of forensic nursing's continued development.

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